

Hydro-elastic analysis of carbon composite marine propeller using co-simulation technique

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Synopsis

Carbon fibre composite has extremely high strength, low density and no corrosion in sea water. These characteristics make it a favourable alternative for consideration as material for marine screw propellers. The obvious advantages are lightweight propeller, resistance to corrosion, and possibly favourable fatigue characteristics. As against this, the relatively higher flexibility of material needs investigation since change of geometry due to load on the blades can affect the hydrodynamic performance. These materials are reduced stiffness and anisotropic in nature, and therefore hydro-elastic based performance analysis is required to understand their performance in operating condition. The current study focuses on numerical investigation for the hydro-elastic based performance analysis of a composite marine propeller in open water condition. The procedure involves the coupling of Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes Equation (RANSE) based Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) solver with the Finite Element Method (FEM) solver using Co-Simulation technique. The open water characteristics including thrust coefficient (K_T), torque coefficient (K_Q), and open water efficiency (η_o) analyzed as a function of the advance ratio (J). This paper presents a comparison of the hydrodynamic performance between the composite propeller and a conventional steel propeller taking into account the structural response under loading. The results for the composite propeller show improved thrust value in comparison with the conventional metallic propeller.

Keywords—Carbon composite propeller Co-simulation, Fluid-Structure Interaction, MRF, Serial coupling, blade deformation, RANSE, FEM.

1. Introduction

Marine propellers are hydrodynamic rotating components designed to deliver thrust to overcome resistance. They are rigid, with fixed geometry and nearly optimized to their maximum performance limit over the past few decades. Some of the conventional propeller materials are manganese bronze, Nickel-Aluminum-Bronze, Aluminum, and steel. The propellers made of these materials are efficient in delivering the thrust. But, they exhibit some unfavorable characteristics such as relatively moderate specific strength (strength to weight ratio), less fatigue cycles, susceptibility to cavitation, corrosion, and relatively more prone to noise, and vibration. It is therefore worthwhile to consider the performance of composite propellers considering the advantages of high specific strength, improved fatigue cycles, and possibility of favourable vibration characteristics. However, due to the relatively lower modulus of elasticity, the composite propeller blades may undergo deformation due to the hydrodynamic and centrifugal loads. The deformation influences the propeller performance by varying the angle of attack. Hence, it is required to perform fluid-structure interaction (FSI) analysis to assess the hydrodynamic performance and structural responses of the propeller.

The earlier studies on composite propeller started in the early 1960s on a Soviet fishing craft where full-scale propellers upto 2m diameter were tested for performance and continued upto 6m in the 1970s. Among the early study on FSI for propellers, Lin H and Lin J (1996) performed hydro-elastic based analysis by coupling lifting surface theory and finite element method. Lin (2005) evaluated the structural performance of the composite blade by nonlinear hydro-elastic analysis. The effect of the fibre stacking sequence on propeller performance was considered along with failure modes. Young (2007) (a) and (2008) (b) studied the composite propeller performance in uniform and wake flow using coupled boundary element method (BEM) - FEM. The study reported the possibility of tailoring the blade rake skew and pitch distribution to improve the performance. Blasques et al. (2010) worked on the design and optimization of the flexible propeller to tailor the flexible laminate to control the deformation shape and subsequently the developed thrust. Ghassemi et al. (2013) presented the finite volume (FVM)-FEM coupling procedure to investigate the flexible propeller. Sangho Han et al. (2015) studied the hydro-elastic performance of marine propeller using CFD-FEM method. Kumar and Wurm (2015) studied the two-way FSI for large deformation of composite propeller blades. Maljaars et al. (2018) conducted experimental studies on the composite propeller and validated BEM and RANSE with FEM coupling methods.

Several potential flow methods like boundary element method, lifting line method can be coupled with the structural solver to perform inviscid FSI analysis. They are computationally cheap and cost-effective solutions in predicting the hydro-elastic based performance of the propellers. However, to capture the complex FSI response it is essential to consider higher fidelity methods.

Based on complexity, computational time and resources, several viscous method based models are available like RANSE, LES, and hybrid RANSE-LES. Among which RANSE is considered to be computationally cheap and effective with a fairly accurate solution. The main objective of the current work is to establish a two-way fluid-structure interaction method for composite marine propeller by using the RANSE solver to compute the hydrodynamic performance and the FEM solver for the structural response. Two geometrically ideal propellers were designed based on the standard series diagram method with material properties of steel and carbon fiber. The section geometry was used unaltered for the carbon composite propeller. The RANSE based commercial program solver STAR-CCM+ v12.04 and ABAQUS 6.14 were coupled for FSI simulation using co-simulation technique. The propeller performance was analyzed in open water condition without any coupling method and compared with regression series data. Then, the FSI effects of the propeller for the different materials were studied at the operating condition with the advance ratio ($J = 0.5$). The deflection of the blade tip and stresses obtained for the two materials were compared. It is found that the composite propeller generates higher thrust than metal at the operating condition.

2. Methodology

This section explains the different stages involved in FSI analysis of composite propeller. It is categorized into four stages, namely selection, design, and development of propeller, fluid model, solid model, mesh generation.

2.1 CAD Model

The propeller parameters were derived from a candidate hull form using appropriate hull propeller interaction components.

The propeller was developed using the Troost Series [12-15] a standard series extensively used for the propeller design. The design incorporates for the Reynolds correction suggested by Oosterveld and Oossanen [10]. The propeller geometry is given in Error! Reference source not found..

Table 1. Propeller Geometry

Propeller diameter (D)	1.785 m
P/D	0.8261
No of Blades (Z)	4
Blade Area Ratio (A_E/A_0)	0.45
RPM	286
Propeller series	Wageningen B series
t/c (at 0.7r)	0.064
Rake angle	15 deg
Skew angle	0 deg
Hub ratio	0.167

The radial sections are generated using empirical relations and wrapped over the cylindrical surface. These sections are lofted using a 3-D CAD software Rhinoceros 5, to obtain final geometry. Fig. 1 illustrates the example of propeller geometry developed using CAD software in different views.

Fig. 1. Propeller geometry in CAD software.

2.2 Fluid analysis

It has been assumed that the working fluid for the study as water with the incompressible and viscous property. Therefore the governing equation of continuity and Navier-Stokes equation with the unsteady and turbulent condition are applicable

$$\left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho U)\right) = 0 \quad - \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + U \cdot \nabla U\right) = \nabla P + \rho g + \mu \nabla^2 U \quad - \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where ρ is the mass density, U is velocity component (u, v, w) in (x, y, z) direction, p is pressure, μ is dynamic viscosity and t is time. Finite volume discretization method used for solving the governing equation with boundary condition. The computational domain has quadrant shape with the $18D$ as length and $2.5D$ as the radius. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the domain details and propeller in CFD domain, respectively.

Fig. 2. Computational domain in CFD

(a)

Fig. 3. A view of Propeller in CFD domain

The propeller was subjected to open water condition where the inflow is uniform with axis-symmetric flow physics. The computational domain consists of two parts, namely the stationary domain and the rotating domain. A conformal Interface was created between the domains that enable to transfer the mass, energy, and continuum quantities.

The interface was created with In-Place topology, i.e., the boundaries are not separated by space. For numerical analysis on rotating bodies Moving reference frame (MRF) method is widely adopted due to the reduction in computational time with less impact on accuracy. This method is also known as "frozen rotor approach" where the motion of the moving part in a specific position and observing the instantaneous flow field with the rotor in that position. MRF method with periodic boundaries was adopted for the study. K- ϵ SST turbulence model considered with two-layer wall Y+ treatment. The simulation performed for the full-scale model for different advance ratio. Physical quantities such as density, dynamic viscosity, inlet velocity (operating condition) were chosen as 997.561 kg/m³, 8.88E-4 Pa.s and 4.25 m/s, respectively.

2.3 Solid model

The general equation of the motion for the propeller blade in the solid model is defined as follows:

$$a\ddot{x} + b\dot{x} + cx = F_T \quad - \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$F_T = F_P + F_{Cent} + F_{Co} + F_{FSI} \quad - \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where \ddot{x}, \dot{x}, x is acceleration, velocity, and displacement components. Furthermore, a, b, c are the mass matrix, stiffness matrix and damping properties of the propeller. Equation 4 represents the total force (F_T) acting on the propeller as the addition of hydrodynamic pressure (F_P), centrifugal force F_{Cent} , forces due to Coriolis effect (F_{Co}), and fluid-structure force (F_{FSI}). The structural behaviors of the propeller were computed by FEM using commercial solver ABAQUS 6.14. Both the propellers were modeled in ABAQUS, one as a homogeneous material with the properties of steel and the other as an anisotropic material with properties of carbon fibre. Due to the complexity of the geometry mesh was unstructured with tetrahedral model. The material properties of the steel and carbon fiber is given in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively.

Table 2 .Material properties for steel propeller

Description	Value
Density (ρ)	7850 kg/m ³
Poisson ratio (ν)	0.3
Young's modulus (E)	210 GPa

Table 3. Material properties for carbon fiber propeller

Description	Value
Density (ρ)	1600 kg/m ³
Young's modulus (E)	
Direction 1 E_{11}	149 GPa
Direction 2 E_{22}	8.83 GPa
Direction 3 E_{33}	8.83 GPa
Poisson ratio (ν)	
ν_{12}	0.342
ν_{13}	0.342
ν_{23}	0.350
Rigidity modulus (G)	
Direction 1 G_{12}	5.38 GPa,
Direction 2 G_{13}	5.38 GPa
Direction 3 G_{23}	2.98 GPa

An interaction interface created for blades and hub to exchange data with CFD Solver. Boundaries of the blades were fixed at the hub. Time increment for both solvers maintained as a constant value. However ABAQUS will automatically change for the convergence.

2.4 Mesh model

In FSI analysis, grid generation is crucial in both the solvers and improper mesh size may result in loss of accuracy. The two solvers use different kinds of mesh models. Accurate data transfer between models is required for transferring forces, wall shear stresses, deformation, etc. This may be affected if interfaces were not matched properly. Therefore, FSI models may require a higher grid count for complex geometries to obtain better results. However, such an approach may be computationally expensive. Based on previous experiences and literature, optimum mesh models were chosen.

The grid independent study carried out for three different mesh size 0.8 million, 1.18 million and 1.8 million and 1.18 million mesh chosen for the study since the difference in thrust value was less than 1 %. An Interface was created between the stationary and rotating domain with In-Plane topology. It was observed that 100% surface matching obtained after initialization.

3.Fluid-Structure Interaction

For any FSI analysis, the fluid model computes the pressure and wall shear stress and solid model calculates deformation and stresses. It is important to create a proper grid and interface between them for data transfer. To connect the independent fluid and structural models, STAR-CCM+ provides an inbuilt Co-Simulation technique. Fig. 4 illustrates the FSI coupling mechanism between the solvers using Co-Simulation technique.

Fig. 4. FSI technique between STAR-CCM+ and ABAQUS [11]

Serial coupling scheme used for data mapping between solvers where, STAR-CCM+ leads the simulation and runs to a preset target time, while Abaqus waits. At the rendezvous time, the solution variables are passed to the Abaqus solver, which then advances to the target time, while the STAR-CCM+ waits. This sequence of steps completes a coupling step, at the end of which the solution quantities are up to date. The data transfer between solvers occurs at every coupling step. Fig. 5 illustrates the serial coupling method.

Fig. 5. Flowchart for the serial coupling method

4.Results and Discussion

The propeller hydrodynamic performance was plotted as a function of thrust coefficient (K_T), torque coefficient (K_Q) and open water efficiency (η_o) against the advance velocity (J). It is clear from **Error! Reference source not found.** that the numerical results had good agreement with the regression data and the error is less than 4%. Furthermore, the hydro-elastic based performance analysis was computed using Co-simulation technique. The open water hydrodynamic performance results of the propeller with two different material properties are presented in Fig. 6. It is identified that the thrust has increased upto 3% in carbon fibre propeller. However the thrust increases as J decreases and decreases as J increases.

Fig. 6. Hydrodynamic performance curves in open water condition for steel and carbon fibre propeller.

The change of angle of attack is maximum at bollard pull condition where maximum deflection is obtained. Unlike metal propeller, the composite material has shown a significant deflection value due to the reduced stiffness and anisotropic property. The structural deflection and stresses obtained from FE solver and blade tip deflection plotted at different advance ratio (J). Fig. 6 illustrates the comparison plot on blade tip deflection for different propeller materials.

Fig. 7. Blade tip deflection for steel and carbon fiber propeller

From the Fig.8, it is observed that the deflection of blade tip at the operating condition for carbon composite propeller is 26.10 times to that of the steel propeller. The carbon fiber will deflect more than metal due to anisotropic property. The deflection plot on the blades is illustrated in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 for steel and carbon propeller respectively. Fig. 11 shows the deformed and undeformed shapes of the composite propeller. Fig. 12 and Fig. 12 illustrates the Von Mises Stress on the propeller at operating condition. The maximum stress for steel and carbon fiber found to be 59.5 MPa and 98.96 MPa respectively. The above stress value ensures that the stresses are well below the failure levels.

Fig. 8 Deflection of steel propeller

Fig. 9. Deflection of carbon fibre composite propeller

Fig. 10. Un-deformed and Deformed form of carbon fibre composite propeller

Fig. 11. Von Mises Stress on Steel propeller

The stress concentration is towards the root for steel propeller and more scattered in case of composite propeller.

Fig. 12. Von Mises Stress on carbon fibre composite propeller

5. Summary and Conclusion

The RANSE based CFD solver is coupled with the FEM solver for the hydro-elastic based analysis on composite propeller. A candidate propeller was designed using series diagram based method.

Numerical FSI investigation were performed in open water condition for steel and carbon composite propeller to estimate the hydrodynamic and structural performance using Co-Simulation technique. The following conclusions were drawn from the study.

- The open water performance results for different materials were compared with regression series data and found good agreement between them.
- Blade deflection at the operating point for steel propeller is 2.16 mm whereas for the carbon composite propeller is 55.8 mm.
- The stress obtained on the steel propeller was 59.5 MPa and carbon composite propeller was 98.96 MPa.
- The thrust values were increased upto 3% in the operating condition for the carbon composite propeller in comparison with steel propeller.
- The stress concentration is towards the root incase of steel propeller and more scattered for the composite propeller.

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